

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D6.1- COMMON INTEGRATED ENVIRONMENTAL-SOCIO-ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

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Summary

With the aim to build an integrated assessment framework, the deliverable defines approaches used to understand and facilitate farm and policy level decisions for soil management practices. The approaches are life cycle assessment, farm level economic analysis, analysis of behavioral intentions from social psychology, integrated farm level sustainability analysis and policy level economic analysis. To build a common integrated framework the theoretical basis and previous empirical applications of our various approaches are presented in a transparent manner based on literature reviews. This environmental-socio-economic framework will then serve to assess the cost and benefits of management practices to enhance soil biodiversity. The assessment links adapted and innovative management practices and related production costs and possibilities to obtain high quality products with higher economic added value by proper management of soil biodiversity. The assessment at societal level includes environmental and socio-economic evaluation of the management practices tested in experiments in WPs 3 and 5 regarding their potential in limiting the negative effects on soil organisms by reducing the use of inorganic fertilizers and pesticides, by contributing to soil biodiversity enhancements through the introduction of innovative cropping systems and management practices. Different data sources provide input for the assessment scheme. With the review of the different strands of socio-economic literature this report lays the theoretical foundation for the research methodology and protocol for integrating the data sets. A common research methodology and protocol for integrating data sets and to build a coherent schedule of progress is needed.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
D6.1	WP6 Environmental and socioeconomic assessment of soil biodiversity management and conservation
Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(s)
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Versions (updates)	Date

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

V1.0

17.06.2021

Deliverable Quality Check		Date	
		17.06.2021	
Planned Delivery Date		Final Delivery Date	
31.01.2021		21.06.2021	
Type of deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	X
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethycs	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

Table of contents

1	INTRODUCTION.....	4
2	APPROACHES TO UNDERSTAND AND SUPPORT SOIL MANAGEMENT DECISIONS: AIM, THEORETICAL BASIS AND CONCEPTS.....	7
2.1	ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT- LCA	7
2.2	FARM LEVEL ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	9
2.3	UNDERSTANDING FARMERS WILLINGNESS TO PARTICIPATE - TPB	11
2.4	INTEGRATED SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT AT FARM LEVEL	12
2.5	POLICY LEVEL ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	15
3	REVIEW OF PREVIOUS EMPIRICAL STUDIES BY APPROACHES	17
3.1	ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT - LCA	17
3.2	FARM LEVEL ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	19
3.3	UNDERSTANDING FARMERS WILLINGNESS TO PARTICIPATE -TPB	20
3.4	INTEGRATED SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENTS.....	22
3.5	POLICY LEVEL ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	24
4	IMPLEMENTATION OF THE APPROACHES IN SOILDIVERAGRO AND THE INTEGRATED APPROACH	26
4.1	ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT – DEVELOPING SOIL BIODIVERSITY FOCUSED LCA ON EXEMPLARY BASIS	26
4.2	FARM LEVEL ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	27
4.3	MEASURING FARMERS INTEREST TO PARTICIPATE -TPB	30
4.4	BUILDING A CUSTOM INTEGRATED SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT AND IMPLEMENTING IT IN SOILDIVERAGRO	31
4.5	MODEL-BASED ASSESSMENT OF POLICY OPTIONS	34
4.6	INTEGRATED APPROACH.....	36
5	CONCLUDING REMARKS.....	38
	REFERENCES.....	39

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

1 Introduction

Healthy and productive soils are necessary for sustainable food, feed and fibre production (FAO and ITPS, 2015). The condition of soil and the level of biodiversity adversely affect the functioning, stability, resilience and adaptability of agro-ecosystems and associated ecosystem services (Wall et al., 2012). Soil conditions such as carbon content and biodiversity are characteristics that can enhance several important ecosystem services: cycling of nutrients, retention and release of water, formation of soil, provision of habitat for biodiversity, food, fuel and fibre production, and perceived existence values associated with biodiversity. The general focus in soil management of using external inputs for yield and the production of food and fiber on short term has had negative effects on many other ecosystem services (e.g., Geiger et al., 2010; Power, 2010; UK NEA, 2011), which undermines the long-term sustainability of agricultural practices (Wall et al., 2012) and further creates the need for using external inputs costly for farms.

The ecosystem services are attained both within and beyond the farm level. Some of the benefits provided by ecosystem services are perceived by farmers both in the short and long run. Besides, there are also benefits that go beyond the farm level and therefore represent public goods. In agriculture, the more environmentally friendly farming practices may appear to be in conflict with farmers' economic goals such as maximization of profit and labor use, particularly in the short term (Hijbeek et al., 2018). Adoption of environmentally sustainable practices related to positive externalities of biodiversity, water, soil, landscapes and climate change, can require substantial investment and long-term commitment for the provision of public goods (Dessart et al., 2019).

Helming et al. (2018) define sustainable soil management (SSM) under high production as integrating "soil functions contributing to ecosystem services and biodiversity, natural and economic resources being utilized efficiently, while farming remains profitable, and production conditions adhere to ethical and health standards". Like sustainable agriculture, SSM thus integrates multiple dimensions that are mutually interdependent. Helming et al. (2018) further state three interconnected research challenges regarding sustainable soil management: (i) understanding the impacts of soil management on soil processes and soil functions; (ii) assessing the sustainability impacts of soil management, taking into account the heterogeneity of geophysical and socio-economic conditions; and (iii) having a systemic understanding of the driving forces and constraints of farmers' decision-making.

Change in the current farming practices is crucial for improving soil conditions and the ecosystem services (Wall et al., 2012). Before large-scale adoption of new management practices and cropping systems that aim to enhance soil genetic and functional biodiversity, environmental and socio-economic analysis is needed to guarantee the real benefits of managing soil organisms for farmers and society. Socio-economic analysis helps also in understanding the factors that influence the farmers' interest in fostering these practices. That is essential for the feasible design and implementation of mechanisms and further tailoring policies.

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Multidisciplinary approaches have been applied previously on soil biodiversity, typically by combining ecological and economic approaches in the context of ecosystem services. For instance, Plaas et al. (2019) built links between economic approach and ecosystem services associated with earthworms. Pascual et al. (2015) illustrated with examples from soil ecology and a simple heuristic model an output value and an insurance value from soil biodiversity. Sidibe et al. (2018) built a bio-economic model showing the link between soil biodiversity and economic rationale of utility maximizing farmers. Banwart et al. (2014) reported the multidisciplinary discussion for soil management policies. Adhikari & Hartemink (2016) stated that soil scientists should engage professionals from other disciplines to further promote the contribution of soils to ecosystem services delivery and human well-being. ES soil studies could be used in local and national policy development and programs on natural resource use and management. These examples show the multidisciplinary approaches to soil biodiversity combining ecological and economic approaches. Multi- or interdisciplinary approaches among social sciences are to be applied to provide valuable insights to farmers' decision making and facilitate policy planning.

This report reviews multidisciplinary approaches that lay the theoretical foundation for the SoilDiverAgro WP6 environmental-socio-economic analysis. The various approaches are presented in a transparent manner, both on farm level and at national and EU level, in order to build a common integrated assessment framework.

Farming practices can be evaluated from different standpoints. On the one hand, there is the identification and quantification of the linkages between soil biodiversity and related ecosystems services in order to undertake environmental assessments of new management practices. In this regard, we present how the *LCA approach* (Hauschild, 2018) can be used to quantify potential environmental impacts of new practices.

On the other hand, there is the identification and quantification of *economic farm data*. This approach aims to assess the impact of the proposed soil biodiversity enhancing management practices on farm profitability, economic risk and resource efficiency and productivity.

Beyond profitability, several social and psychological factors affect soil management at farm level. The *theory of planned behavior* (Ajzen, 1991) supports understanding and modelling farmers' decision making behaviour by assessing the role of attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural controls of farmers (Sok et al., 2020).

The previously mentioned theoretical approaches are equally important for overall farm sustainability and thus demands an *integrated sustainability assessment* that takes into account environmental, economic, social and governance dimensions and allows the analysis of trade-offs and synergies between the dimensions (FAO, 2013). Accordingly, this report will develop a *multi-criteria analysis* to perform an integrated sustainability assessment of practices on farm level.

Assessment of new management practices and cropping systems beyond farm and regional level with regard to their implementation potential requires to consider also the related costs and benefits at national and EU level too. A *cost-benefit analysis* (CBA) is a well established approach to assess the soil

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biodiversity enhancing management practices on policy level. Thus summarizing in a common unit (euros) the balance between cost and benefits from a social point of view.

Finally, encouraging farmers for the adoption of better soil management practices has an effect on food markets. *Market models* allow simulation of these effects. The *scenario techniques* and simulations allow assessing the economic performance of management alternatives.

Summarising, the aim of this deliverable is to review the selected environmental-socio-economic approaches to evaluate management practices that aim to increase soil biodiversity on agricultural lands. We discuss the applicability of these approaches, their pros and cons and possible links and synergies between approaches. We review the key empirical studies using these approaches. Based on the literature reviews we build a common integrated framework in SoildiverAgro WP6 that will serve to assess the management practices to enhance soil biodiversity. Different theoretical strands lay the foundation of this integrated framework. This assessment framework itself provides a combination of methodologies which aims to pursue coherent data collection in the different study cases, and allows for comparative analysis.

2 Approaches to understand and support soil management decisions: aim, theoretical basis and concepts

Farmers are the key decision makers in soil management. In their decisions, they can take into account the multiple dimensions of sustainability: monetary revenue that farm production generates; protection and enhancement of natural resources, such as soil quality; and social and cultural aspects of farming. Farmers are increasingly challenged to include environmental, economic and social aspects of sustainability in designing their farming systems. This affects the three mutually dependent aspects of farmers' decision making, and calls for assessment of farming systems via indicators. These in turn can help farmers in reorienting their farm production towards environmental, social and economic sustainability at the farm level.

In their typology of assessment tools Gasparatos and Scolobig (2012) identify three main groups, which they distinguish based on their valuation system and perspective, the role of the participant and their stance on reductionism. A first group, the monetary tools (e.g. cost accounting, cost-benefit analysis and valuation tools) are anthropocentric, focus on the individual and are often reductionist. Second, biophysical tools (e.g. LCA) are eco-centric, exclude human preferences and are reductionist. A third group of tools are the indicator tools (e.g. multi criteria assessment). In multi-criteria assessments, using a set of indicators both the valuation perspective, the role of the participant and the stance on reductionism are often mixed, as different methodological choices may be made for each indicator. All types of approaches have been identified as relevant for the evaluation of soil management practices. In the following sections, we elaborate biophysical approaches, their aims, theoretical bases and concepts (2.1), monetary approaches (2.2 and 2.5) and indicator based multi criteria assessment (2.4). Furthermore we present an approach that is not aiming to assess management practices by decision makers but to understand decision makers' behavior (2.3).

2.1 Environmental assessment- LCA

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) covers environmental assessment, and includes the full production chain. It is defined by the European Commission as an internationally standardized scientific methodology aimed to study the environmental impacts of goods and services. It takes into account the full cycle from the raw material extraction, through transformation, manufacturing, transport, use and end-of-life.

The relevant emissions, energy and material resources related to human activities are quantified in every stage and then classified into impact categories by a Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method

(ILCD 2010). These impact categories can describe midpoint consequences (climate change, ozone depletion, etc.) or endpoint consequences (loss of biodiversity, damage to human health). In both cases, the interpretation of the assessment must follow a multi-criteria and multi-category baseline in order to avoid burden shifting when studying the consequences of innovative goods, services or management approaches.

Nowadays, the indispensable framework for LCA is provided by the ISO 14040 and 14044, although several standardization and harmonization initiatives have been developed or are in current development. According to ISO 14040 (ISO 2006), the study must be divided in 4 phases:

- Goal and scope definition: the objectives of the study, its potential use and the target audience are defined in this section. The system product, functional unit, system boundaries and main assumptions and limitations should also be described in the goal and scope.
- Inventory analysis: all the data concerning inputs and outputs from and to the ecosphere and technosphere, such as material and energy resources and emissions are collected in the life cycle inventory (LCI) referred to the functional unit previously defined.
- Impact assessment: the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) stage is driven by a LCIA method which provides the classification rules and characterisation factors (CFs). In this stage, the elementary flows are classified into impact categories and the CFs describe their relevance for a give impact category.
- Interpretation: the results must be interpreted to extract the final conclusion according to the objectives of the study.

The ISO standards 14040 and 14044 do not recommend using any specific LCIA method, but according to the ISO 14044, the selected impact categories “shall reflect a comprehensive set of environmental issues related to the product system being studied, taking the goal and scope into consideration” (Hauschild, 2018). However, some organisations do provide more specific recommendations. For example, the European Commission has published recommendations for midpoint and endpoint impact categories by evaluating all relevant existing approaches per impact category, leading to the recommendation of the best available approach and the development of the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) method (ILCD, 2010). The method includes 12 midpoint impact categories (climate change, stratospheric ozone depletion, human toxicity, particulate matter formation, ionizing radiation, photochemical ozone formation, acidification, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, land use, water use and resource use) and three endpoint areas of protection (human health, natural environment, natural resources).

LCA methodologies and impact assessment methods have evolved significantly in 50 years. In the 1970s the efforts of impact assessment on the food sector were firstly focused in reducing the impacts associated with packaging but, after the 1990s, full production processes were included in a full assessment, first called Resource and Environmental Profile Analyses. The emergence of LCA methodologies (Gaillard, 2005) and environmental policies have pushed the development of

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environmental impact assessments of food supply chains with different purposes: R&D and business strategy support, eco-design of products and processes, divulgation, support to environmental innovative solutions, communication among stakeholders, labelling or environmental product declarations (EPDs), etc. Ecolabels based on LCA for food products exist (such as Green Crane) although the European Commission did not create an EU Ecolabel for food and feed products due to difficulty to measure the impacts in the production stage, the variability of results due to region, technology and product, high cost to develop reliable LCA on agriculture products, etc. (Oakdene Hollins, 2011). The development of consistent methodologies for agriculture products would lead to use of LCA results to support policy making in the sector.

In private companies, the use of LCA is becoming more popular since Unilever created a software for the LCA of margarine production (Bloemhof-Ruwaard et al., 1995). Since then, the development of specific software for LCA (such as SimaPro or Gabi) has allowed the application of LCA in the decision-making phase of private institutions and researchers from every life cycle stage (from crop management to end-of-life of packaging, for example). More recently, LCA has been also used to develop informing and design tools, such as the GEOFootPrint tool (geoFootprint 2020) that displays the regionalized environmental impacts and its sources of several crops.

Farmers managing soil should build the habits of collaborating with LCA practitioners to build and update data inventories in a practical way to provide meaningful and high quality data without compromising their time resources. By other hand, the results and conclusions obtained from LCA studies developed by different authors are only comparable if the same assessment methods and methodologies have been used, thus harmonization is a key step towards the applicability of LCA in all types of management frameworks, including soil management.

2.2 Farm level economic analysis

The adoption of new farming practices is a complex process that is driven by numerous factors (environmental, social, institutional, behavioural, economic). Of special relevance are farmer's awareness, knowledge and perception about the feasibility of the technology to be adopted and its potential to contribute to the fulfilment of farmer's objectives (Pannell, 1999). Consequently, profitability is a key aspect of the adoption decision process. Demonstrating the economic implications of adopting more sustainable farming practices requires assessing whether the costs derived from such adoption can be compensated by their benefits.

The farm level economic analysis of soil biodiversity enhancement practices aims to assess the impact of the practices on crop profitability, resource use efficiency and productivity under various pedoclimatic conditions, paying special attention to the reduction in the use of mineral fertilizers and pesticides going along with practices. The end is to provide impact estimates resulting from the analysed practices on crop profitability (changes in input use intensity and crop yield).

Consequently, the basis for such analysis would be the experimental activities regarding farming practices, input use and crop production, to be able to assess and to demonstrate how the farming practices can contribute to revenues and production costs. However, some costs, such as machinery depreciation, are usually specific to each farm and can be subject to a large variability. In principle, the farming practices to be field-tested are not expected to affect indirect production costs. For this reason the analysis at the farm level can be limited at the crop level, analysing the impact of the soil biodiversity enhancing management practices on crop's gross margin. Gross margin (GM) is defined as the difference between revenue (value of production plus subsidies) and all variable costs directly attributable to each crop (Turner and Taylor, 1998).

The assessment of the profitability for farmers of alternative agricultural practices or technologies can be approached in different ways, usually contingent on the research's objectives and data availability. In any case, assessing the relative profitability of different agricultural practices/technologies requires some definition of the production and cost functions, i.e. of the implications of the analysed practice/technology on production (changes in crop yield and/or quality) and/or production costs (changes in input use intensity).

A first approach would rely on the *econometric analysis of farm survey data*. Data from a sample of farms can be used to estimate economic indicators (e.g. production/cost/revenues/profit functions) by relating those with technological choices (e.g. farming practices or agricultural technologies implemented in the farms). While having the advantage of relying on the use of real data from commercial farms, this approach requires that the farming practices/technologies analysed be already implemented in a sufficient number of the surveyed farms, what reduces the applicability of econometric tools in the case of new practices/technologies that have not, or barely have, being implemented on commercial farms.

Additionally, farming practices/technologies whose profitability is analysed are usually defined in a very generic way (e.g., minimum tillage versus conventional tillage, organic farming versus conventional farming), without entering in detail regarding how each practice is being implemented. For example, by differentiating between different crop rotation alternatives or different tillage intensities or fertilizer dosage, etc. This could be solved by collecting more detailed information on how each farmer is implementing a given farming practice/technology.

A second approach for economic assessment of farming practices and technologies is combining *partial budgeting with experimental field data*. Partial crop budgeting consists of calculating the effect on profitability of changes in the crop production process, either in terms of changes in production costs, crops yields or farm prices. This approach is more suitable when the focus of the analysis is more detailed or when the analysed technologies are in an experimental phase and are not implemented in commercial farms, as it is the case in the SoildiverAgro project. The basis for any partial budgeting is the elaboration of a detailed technical-economic characterisation of the crop production process in terms of farming practices, crop yields, input use and production costs, from which detailed budgets can be built to integrate changes in input use and output for competing practices.

A related alternative approach is bio-economic modelling, which rely both on crop growth models to produce computer simulations of the biophysical performance of alternative farming practices/technologies, and economic modelling (from partial crop budgeting to agro-economic models) to assess their relative profitability.

2.3 Understanding farmers willingness to participate - TPB

The scientific literature has searched for universal patterns in factors influencing adoption of soil conservation practices, but Meta-analyses showed that most factors have an inconsistent and in fact mostly insignificant impact (Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007; Wauters & Matthijs, 2014). Wauters & Matthijs (2014) partially attribute this to the importance of context, which is related to particularities of the regions, just as to attributes of the practices themselves. As classic adoption variables often fail to understand adoption decisions, several authors have been emphasizing the importance of studying social-psychological variables.

The theory of planned behavior (TPB) is the theoretical framework the most frequently used approach by different disciplines to study social- psychological factors and antecedents of individuals' behavior (Ajzen, 1988; Ajzen, 1991). Social-psychological variables reflect a persons' motivation, attitude, beliefs and preferences related to a particular behavior. Their assessment by TPB framework may reveal drivers and barriers for adoption of the soil management practices by farmers. TPB builds on the notion that the propensity for behavior depends on the formation of behavioral intention by the individual. The development of intention however, is determined by the attitudes towards the action, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980; Ajzen, 1987; Ajzen, 1991).

According to the theory of planned behavior, farmers' intention to adopt a practice is determined by the degree to which implementing it is evaluated positively or negatively by the farmer (attitude), the feeling of social pressure from others (called referents) to adopt the practice (subjective norm) and the beliefs of the farmers about the ease or difficulty of successfully applying it (perceived behavioral control) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Theory of planned behavior

- Attitude is formed by the belief that the behavior is associated with a set of outcomes, weighted by an evaluation of these outcomes. The latter is the value given by the farmer to this outcome: e.g. how important it is to him/her to have good soil structure.
- Subjective norm is determined by how much the farmer perceives others (called referents) think he/she should adopt the practice and by a farmers' motivation to comply with these referents.
- Finally, perceptions of behavioral control are determined by the belief that a set of control factors facilitate or obstruct the behavior, weighted by the expected impact that these factors would have if they were to be present. All these underlying subjective beliefs influence a farmers' intention to adopt a practice, and are acting as cognitive drivers or barriers which encourage or discourage the farmer to adopt it.

Combining attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control, results in a positive or negative intention to actually perform the behavior. According to the theory of planned behavior, the greater the farmers' intention to adopt the practice, the more likely one is to actually act on it as well.

There are some criticism on TBP, which includes reliance on self-reporting, the lack of specifics in the operationalization of cognitions and constructs for synthetic rather than analytic truths and testable hypothesis (Ogden, 2003), the predictive validity of intentions for actual behavior, underestimation of irrational behavior, role of affect and emotion, past behavior (Ajzen, 2011). Despite the criticism, it is acknowledged that TPB is an accessible and empirically grounded conceptual framework with well-established guidelines for measuring social-psychological constructs and building theory (Sok et al., 2020).

2.4 Integrated sustainability assessment at farm level

The Brundtland report defines *sustainability* as: "Development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (WCED, 1987). The FAO's elaborated definition of *sustainable agriculture* is: "the management and conservation of the natural resource base, and the orientation of technological change in such a manner as to ensure the attainment of continued satisfaction of human needs for present and future generations. Sustainable agriculture conserves land, water, and plant and animal genetic resources, is environmentally non-degrading, technically appropriate, economically viable and socially acceptable" (FAO, 1988).

While *sustainability assessment* originally mainly focussed on the environmental impacts of farming (e.g. van der Werf & Petit, 2002; Payraudeau & van der Werf, 2005), in recent decades it has been acknowledged that the environmental, social and economic dimension of sustainability need to be evaluated simultaneously in an integrated assessment (Hardi and Zdan, 1997; Kates et al., 2005; Hurni and Osman-Elasha, 2009; FAO, 2013; Schindler et al., 2015). This allows to reveal trade-offs and synergies within the system. Sustainability assessment is "conducted for supporting decision-making and policy in a broad environmental, economic and social context, and transcends a purely technical/scientific evaluation" (Sala et al., 2015). It aims to direct decision-making towards sustainability (Pope et al., 2017).

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In SoildiverAgro the focus is on decision-making by farmers, more specifically on decisions about implementing agricultural practices to improve soil biodiversity. Sustainability assessment will provide insights on the impact of these practices on overall farm sustainability, i.e. on the different dimensions of sustainability and the trade-offs between them. Sustainability assessment thus provides support to direct farm management towards more sustainability.

A sustainability assessment should be based on a solid conceptual framework (Sala et al., 2015). The Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems (**SAFA**), was proposed by the FAO (2013). SAFA offers a holistic framework, with the guiding vision that food and agricultural systems worldwide are characterized by four dimensions of sustainability, i.e. the three that are traditionally considered: environmental integrity, economic resilience and social well-being, plus the newly introduced “good governance”. SAFA outlines the essential elements of these dimensions in 21 themes, e.g. for the environmental dimension: atmosphere, water, land, biodiversity, materials and energy, and animal welfare. The themes are further divided into 58 sub-themes, e.g. for atmosphere: greenhouse gases and air quality. An overview is given in Figure 2.

One of the first steps in the sustainability *assessment process* is determining the assessment level or operational boundaries (FAO, 2013; Schader et al., 2014). If the measures to increase soil biodiversity are implemented at the farm level, the integrated sustainability assessment needs to be performed at that level. The farm gate serves as a system boundary. Direct effects from farming activities are assessed, as well as indirect effects caused by farm inputs. Upstream effects beyond the farm gate are however not taken into account (e.g. by transport or further processing of farm outputs).

In the next step, the conceptual framework needs to be made more concrete by a *sustainability assessment tool*, i.e. an analytical tool that can facilitate the assessment by measuring and monitoring sustainability (Gasparatos and Scolobig, 2012). Such tools can be sets of models and/or indicators, structured within a software or application. *Indicators* are variables, which point to, provide information about, or describe the state of phenomena, which are difficult to measure directly. They measure performance or reflect changes in activities, projects or programs. Indicators are considered easy-to-use tools for farmers, because they simplify the complex system, inform and encourage decision-making (Girardin et al., 1999; Hák et al., 2007; UNAIDS, 2010). Three types of indicators can be distinguished: (1) target-based indicators, assess whether plans or policies are in place, e.g. “Has the farm set itself a target to conserve biodiversity?”; (2) practice-based indicators, also called means-based, refer to indicators that assess farm practices or technical means, e.g. “Which practices does the farm implement that are known to enhance populations?”; (3) Performance-based indicators, also called effect-based or result-oriented, are used to assess the impact of practices, e.g. “What is the species diversity and abundance on the farm?” (FAO, 2013: 56-59). From (1) to (3) the relevance of the indicators usually increases, while the feasibility of measurement decreases (Payraudeau and Van der Werf, 2005). The indicator type used is thus an important determinant for the complexity of sustainability assessment tools (Coteur et al., 2020).

Many farm level sustainability assessment tools have been developed, reflecting the variety and complexity of agricultural systems and the variety of sustainability perceptions. Classifying SATs

according to their complexity and the steps in the farmer's strategic decision making process they support, revealed that some tools provide only a weak link to the farmer's decision making process.

Figure 2: SAFA framework with the four dimensions of sustainability and the themes and subthemes in each dimension

Hence, for a SAT to incite action towards sustainable farm development it should be farm(er) focused. Moreover, the assessment process should also include support beyond the mere implementation of the tool, i.e. in interpreting the SATs results, developing improvement strategies and implementing them. Interaction between farmers, advisors and experts in all steps and even in the development of the SAT has great added value (Coteur et al., 2020).

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2.5 Policy level economic analysis

International and EU-level processes increasingly raise concerns for the incorporation of soil management practices in policy level analyses. With the recognition that soils are essential for sustainable development, in an international commitment soil quality was directly targeted with the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Keesstra et al., 2016). Although belowground biodiversity is not explicitly mentioned in the SDGs, there is a growing awareness amongst scientists and governments that healthy soils and soil biodiversity are interdependent, and that reductions in soil biodiversity render soils more vulnerable to other degradation processes (Plaas et al., 2019). The strong connection between soil quality and food provision is made visible in SDG 2 on food security, which says that by 2030 sustainable food production systems should be insured by implementing resilient agriculture practices that improve soil quality. Targeting soil quality in new policy frameworks, actors such as farmers, landowners and agricultural businesses receive incentives to make a transition towards increasing use of sustainable practices and enhance ES provisioning.

First, conventional agriculture (CA) is increasingly facing threats from soil degradation, such as compaction, erosion, organic matter decline, and soil biodiversity loss. The European Commission (2006) identified these threats in the proposal for a Soil Framework Directive, which was finally withdrawn in May 2014 (for background and reasons see Glaesner et al., 2014). These threats are already stabilizing maximum yields at current levels despite increased management efficiency, and can be expected to further impact food production and the economy of agronomical businesses by gradually reducing crop yields and quality (farmers' profitable income) as well as an erosion of buffering capacity to future increased incidences of extreme events affecting agriculture, e.g. heavy rainfall, droughts, or heat-waves that may cause partial or complete crop loss (farmers' income security) (Collaku et al., 2002).

Second, under the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) regulations farmers are encouraged to include practices that involve 'ecological intensification'. Depending on CAP instruments being developed and evaluated, and depending on specific implementation by Member States, CAP payments for 'greening agriculture' measures may increase the application of farming practices that help to close nutrient cycles (cover crops, green fertilizers, organic manure) and decrease land use intensity (reduced tillage, multiple-crop rotations cycles including grasses/cereals) (Van Doorn et al., 2017). These measures are likely to increase soil biodiversity in general. But we are looking inside the complexity to find out more about useful tools to stimulate soil biota for healthy soils with farm management options.

Third, bringing together the interests of farming and nature conservation may result in 'nature inclusive agriculture'. With the second pillar of the common agricultural policy (CAP), the EU's rural development policy is designed to support rural areas and meet the wide range of economic, environmental and societal challenges in the member countries. CAP Pillar II instruments could be developed to promote farming measures that aim to conserve and enhance aboveground biodiversity

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(e.g. game crops, set-aside, and wildlife seed mixtures, fallow land, field margins and flower strips, beetle banks, wood shingles and other green veins in the landscape). These interventions will also enhance natural enemies for pest control as well as provide habitat for wild pollinators (insects, birds and mammals). Also, indirectly, soil biodiversity in agricultural fields will profit from these measures as the surrounding landscape elements provide opportunity for recolonization after disturbances from tillage (Frazao et al., 2017) or extreme weather events.

The sustainability threats from soil degradation faced by conventional agriculture are proactively dealt with in CAP orientations on greening agricultural production. This way, the Commission expresses intentions to support a sustainability transition by providing flexibility to shifting from first to second pillar payments for Member states. Although the implementation of such a shift by member states in budget allocation has been limited, the mechanism provides anchor points for policy level economic analysis. In this project we explore the questions to what extent the assessment schemes should take into account resistance towards such a sustainability transition, reflected in the implemented policy frameworks; should new policies economically support such a sustainability shift by implementing available measures in first and second CAP pillars or more general innovation funds?

A *cost-benefit analysis* (CBA) that summarizes in a common unit the balance between cost and benefits from a social point of view, is used in SoilDiverAgro to assess the soil biodiversity enhancing management practices on policy level. CBA allows to identify all costs and benefits directly and indirectly linked to the regulation or project, and subsequently their valuation in monetary terms (Pearce et al., 2006; Hanley, 2001). The LCA approach outlined in previous sections will allow SoilDiverAgro to make an assessment about the environmental impacts of alternative farm practices. It will provide results for different impact categories on physical units.

CBA will require not only the quantification of avoided externalities in physical units but also their monetary valuation. Based on the CBA, new CAP policy measures, targeted to reduce the level of intensity with a significant reduction in fertilizer and pesticide application, will be assessed here. Many of the environmental damages assessed by the LCA through different impact categories are not exchanged in markets. Therefore, CBA should be based on the calculation of shadow prices, i.e., estimated prices for goods that are not traded in markets. There are two methodologies available to estimate shadow prices: the abatement and the damage cost approaches. SoilDiverAgro will not carry out a direct estimation of shadow prices for externalities identified by the LCA, instead, we will apply the benefit transfer methodology.

The results of the CBA- and LCA-approaches will enter the model-based analyses in SoilDiverAgro. This model-based approach, however, will be applied at a more aggregated level which looks at the impact of new CAP instruments and its consequences at the national and international market level. The general equilibrium market model will illustrate the consequences of the new CAP instruments with the adjustment of agricultural production practices on yields, prices and trade.

3 Review of previous empirical studies by approaches

In this chapter, we review how the approaches described in Chapter 2 have been used in previous empirical studies in the case of soil management practices. In some cases, empirical examples from soil management were few and focus in review was in the agricultural management practices in general.

3.1 Environmental assessment - LCA

Soil management approaches influence the environmental performance of the activity assessed and the evaluation method is still under development. As comparability is only possible when the same methods and methodologies have been used, harmonization is a requirement for the applications that support policy and decision-making. The development of soil management impact assessment has been linked to several initiatives, shown in Table 1.

Methodologies, impact assessment methods and databases have been developed in parallel to assess the environmental impacts of the agriculture sector (SALCA, MEXA LCA, Agrybalise) and to ease the access to reliable data. The newest guidelines are based on the experience gained within the years of application of previous guidelines. They try to establish common approaches to deal with specific agriculture aspects, such as the pesticides and fertilizers modelling, the CO₂ uptake, the degradation of soil or the impacts derived from land use change. Other issues, such as impacts on ecosystem services, are less developed and are being currently assessed to include them in future LCA methodologies (Liu et al., 2019).

Harmonizing the methodologies is not easy as they are in constant development and the goal and scope of LCAs for agricultural products can vary depending on the sub-sector and product type. Forestry, horticulture, bio-economy (bio-energy, bio-based materials, etc.) or crop production need different approaches to carry out the LCA given the huge difference among these sub-sectors. In consequence, the development of Product Category Rules (PCRs) for specific products is one approach proposed by the European Commission to enable reliable comparison of results among products and ease the communication of results. In PCRs, the system boundaries and the functional unit (FU) is defined for a specific product, narrowing down the options for the selection of the FU, given that it can be defined according to land management criteria (ha*year, with the goal to minimize land use intensity), productivity (MJ or kg, to enhance eco-efficiency) or financial criteria (monetary units to optimize economic efficiency) (Nemecek, 2013).

Table 1. Relevant initiatives for the harmonization of agri-food LCA.

Name	Type	Year	Organization	Description
Swiss Agricultural Life Cycle Assessment (SALCA)	LCIA method	2009	Agroscope	Originally LCIA method adapted for agricultural conditions for Switzerland and extended to other European countries.
Livestock environmental Assessment and Performance Partnership LEAP (LEAP 2020)	LCA methodological guidelines	2012	FAO	Multi-stakeholder initiative to assess the environmental performance of livestock supply chains, including feed production by cultivation.
ENVIFOOD protocol (EUROPEAN FOOD... 2013)	LCA methodological guidelines	2013	European Commission	European initiative for environmental assessment of food and drink, which include a protocol to develop the life cycle of food and drink products, complementary to PEF guides.
Product Environment Footprint (Zampori & Pant 2019)	LCA methodological guidelines	2013	European Commission	Initiative to develop harmonized methodology to carry out LCAs of products. LCA experts developed PEF together with industry representants. Product Category Rules (PEFCR) were created to develop rules for specific families of products. Methodological guidelines to develop LCAs and further PCRs were developed and improved after testing them within the industry (Zampori & Pant, 2019) The project is currently in the last phase: transition phase and recommends the use of LANCA v2.2 for soil quality assessment.
Product Category Rules (PCR 2020, Single market... 2020)	PCRs	2014	EPDs operators, European Commission (PEFCRs)	Product Category Rules are a verified document which sets the rules to carry out an LCA for a specific type of products and allow the comparison of results.
HortiFootprint Category Rules (Helmes, 2020)	PCR	2020	Ministerie van LNV	Product category rules using PEF principles. Tomatoes, phalaenopsis, apples, bananas, roses and tulip bulbs were assessed to build the PCR.

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Regarding soil related impacts, they have been usually addressed via the midpoint impact category of land use, which contributes to endpoint impact categories such as biodiversity loss, damage to human health or depletion of natural resources. In addition, soil management approaches also influence other midpoint impact categories (climate change, use of fossil resources, eco toxicity or human toxicity). Usually, impacts on the soil quality are aimed to be calculated although the selection of a stand-alone representative indicator is challenging given the temporal and spatial variation of the relevancy of different soil properties.

The UNEP-SETA LCA highlights the importance of building consensus on the impact pathway to assess biodiversity impacts derived from soil management and land use. Currently, soil management and land intensity data (chemical inputs, irrigation, introduction of new species, crop rotation, etc.) are used to develop midpoint indicators. In Europe, the model recommended by ILCD was the one by Brandão & Canals (2013), which uses the Soil Organic Matter (SOM) as stand-alone indicator to describe soil quality due to its high applicability (Vidal-Legaz et al., 2016). Later, in the framework of the European Footprint project, the LANCA® v 2.2 model was recommended due to the inclusion of more indicators in an aggregated value: erosion resistance, mechanical filtration, groundwater replenishment and biotic production (physico-chemical filtration was excluded due to the high correlation with the mechanical filtration).

Then the impact pathway towards the evaluation of impacts on biodiversity must be done in parallel, as well as the calculation of the environmental impacts in other midpoint categories such as climate change. For climate change impacts or CO₂ release caused by land use and land transformation, the use of the most recent IPCC is internationally used and accepted. Jolliet et al. (2014) pointed out that in order to better understand the link between land use and the provision of ecosystem services and biodiversity loss, we first need to assess the impact of land occupation and transformation on soil quality and its functions. Thus, within the impact pathway proposed for land use, the latter study includes a set of indicators to determine the impacts on soil quality (e.g. soil fertility, soil stability) and the impacts on habitats (e.g. fragmentation, degradation) which lead to the loss of soil and ecosystems. Although this is a valuable step in recognizing the relevance of soil, impacts addressing soil functions are still under-characterized and an in-depth understanding of the connections between mid and endpoint indicators is still required (Vidal-Legaz et al., 2016). Also, local circumstances should be better taken into account in emission models of some impact categories (Notarnicola et al., 2016), for example toxicity (Rosenbaum et al., 2015). Furthermore, the methods for the assessment of land use impacts on ecosystem services (Hu et al., 2008) of soil erosions and quality degradation (De Laurentiis et al., 2019), water depletion (Caldeira et al., 2018) and nutrient use efficiency (Akram et al., 2019) have been under active development in the recent years.

3.2 Farm level economic analysis

The *econometric analysis of farm survey data* has been used in empirical studies in the cases of established farming methods. For example, Rasul and Thapa (2004) used data from a sample of

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farms to compute profitability indicators for both conventional and organic production in Bangladeshi agricultural systems, while Schimmelpennig (2018) assesses the impact of precision agriculture techniques on the profitability of US soybean cropping using official survey data. A vast literature has also used this approach to analyse technical and cost efficiency in agricultural production and to compare different agricultural technologies. For example, Mayen et al. (2010) compare technical efficiency of both conventional and organic production systems in dairy farms of the US, while Oumer et al. (2020) compare the cost-efficiency of sustainable farming practices in Ethiopian corn farms.

Partial crop budgeting is the most common tool used to analyse the profitability of alternative agricultural practices and technologies (Swinton and Lowenberg-DeBoer, 1998). A vast number of applications of partial crop budgeting based on experimental field data exists. To name a few studies with relation to the type of farming practices considered in SoildiverAgro: Jackson et al (2004) assess the impact of tillage and organic matter management alternatives on the profitability of Californian horticulture; Sartori et al (2005) assess the impact of crop rotations and organic farming on the production costs of several arable crops in Italy; Aryal et al (2015) analyse the impact of zero tillage on the profitability of wheat production in NW India; Adamtey et al. (2016) compare the effect of both conventional and organic production systems on input productivity and profitability in Kenya corn production; Yost et al. (2019) assess the long-term profitability of precision agriculture techniques and soil conservation practices in corn-soybean rotations in Missouri; and Kumar et al (2018) analyse the impact of sustainable farming practices, related to tillage, crop diversification and precision agriculture techniques on the productivity and profitability of Indian cereal production.

A related alternative approach, *bio-economic modelling*, was used for example, by Sattler et al. (2020) to analyse the impact of alternative farming practice (including tillage, fertilization, weed and pest control and harvesting) on the profitability of relevant crops in Germany.

3.3 Understanding farmers willingness to participate - TPB

Based on TPB it is expected that more positive attitudes towards environment, social pressure and perceived control, impact farmers the intention towards the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (Adnan et al., 2017), also in soil conservation (Arbuckle and Roesch-McNally, 2015, Hijbeek et al., 2018).

Sok et al. (2020) review on how TPB has been applied in the research of farm management indicated that TPB has been most actively used in research on crop management practices such as disease control, farming systems such as organic, issues regarding participation in agri-environmental schemes, and soil management. Livestock management has received somewhat less attention with papers mostly focusing on grassland management, biosecurity and disease control and animal welfare research.

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In their meta-analysis, Wauters and Matthijs (2014) found almost all studies on applying TPB for the adoption of soil conservation practices were conducted in the USA, Canada or Australia. While there is abundant literature on the adoption of agri-environmental measures and schemes in Europe, they concluded that in Europe less attention has been given to soil conservation. However, in recent years, some studies have been published, applying the theory of planned behavior to gain insight into adoption of soil conservation practices across Europe (Wauters and Mathijs, 2013; Viaene et al., 2016; Hijbeek et al., 2018; Werner et al., 2017; Bijttebier et al., 2018; Bechini et al., 2020).

More positive attitudes towards environment, social pressure and perceived control, impact the intention to the use of cover crops (Arbuckle and Roesch-McNally, 2015) or the intention to increase soil organic matter (Hijbeek et al., 2018). The results from TPB scientific literature concerning perceived behavioral control have been ambiguous, as some studies found no differences between intenders and non-intenders, while some others found differences in extent to which particular control factors could impede adoption of the practices (Werner et al., 2017). Lack of impact of subjective norms on intention is also found by Niles et al. (2016) in studying climate change mitigation strategies. The attitudes and norms from the social reference groups and behavioral control were also affected by the farm characteristics and socio-demographic factors, such as farming intensity, soil texture, and farmer's age (also Fang et al., 2018).

The mere knowledge that attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control influence intention/behavior is useful, but not enough to develop potentially effective interventions, with respect to extension and communication, policy and research. To this end, some studies focus on the elicitation of subjective beliefs that precede underlying attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control (e.g. Beedell and Rehman, 1999; Fielding et al., 2005; Wauters and Mathijs, 2013; Werner et al., 2017; Bijttebier et al., 2018). Subjective beliefs are assumed to provide the cognitive and affective foundations for attitudes, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioral control. It is found that farmers with positive intentions to adopt believe positive outcomes as being more likely to occur than non-intenders (Werner et al., 2017). Positive intenders were also more stimulated by their social environment, i.e. the influential referents (e.g. agricultural organization, neighbours, government, etc.).

Regional variation in subjective beliefs across different regions in Europe have been found (Bijttebier et al., 2018). Although Bijttebier et al. (2018) observed some shared beliefs across regions, such as the belief that non-inversion tillage leads to less labour and fuel needs but to more problems with weeds, pests and/or diseases, other beliefs were restricted to only one or some regions, confirming earlier findings that adoption is highly context and case specific, so much that particular variables do have different influences in different cases.

Menzio et al. (2015) also discuss the importance of the capacity, i.e. control beliefs on the availability of necessary knowledge and skills in development of intention to adopt environmental measures. The actual capacity to implement behavior in everyday practices requires attention in design of policies aiming to facilitate more environmentally friendly behavior.

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However, the theory of planned behavior does not provide a full explanation of intention or behavior. In a meta-analysis of the TPB, Armitage and Conner (2001) revealed that the TPB accounted for 39% of the variance in behavior intention. Some studies, specifically conducted on soil conservation practices in Europe, reported a higher predictive ability (up to 70%) of the model (Wauters et al., 2010; Werner et al., 2017). In order to increase the predictive ability of the model, several researchers have added new constructs to the basic TPB, among which the concept of moral norm. Botetzagias et al. (2015) indicated that moral norms, situational factors and past behavior are the ones most commonly used and generally perceived as enhancing the predictive ability of the standard constructs of TPB. Other studies also included self-identity, perception of mass media, environmental knowledge and perceived habit (or lack of it) of sustainable practices.

Instead of adding constructs to improve predictive ability of TPB, other authors suggest to use alternative behavioural models to analyse the impact of psychological variables on adoption (Greiner, 2015). For example motivational profiles have been found to significantly correlate with farmers' perceptions about what constrained them from implementing conservation practices. In addition, these profiles also explained differences in farmers' perceptions of and stated propensity to interact with policy instruments. Although these motivational profiles are to some extent covered by TPB, exploring the added value and compatibility of alternative behavioral models might be worthwhile.

3.4 Integrated sustainability assessments

Sustainable soil management (SSM) impacts on multiple targets (or sustainability themes), as well as trade-offs and synergies between them. (Helming et al., 2018). These authors state that an integrated assessment of SSM can provide a scientific evidence base for decision making at different levels. However, none of the tools they refer to integrates all sustainability themes. Here, we therefore review overall sustainability assessment tools for the farm level, for their potential to assess the sustainability of soil management.

Integrated sustainability assessment tools (ISATs) (or multi-criteria assessments) have been developed and used for many purposes, including monitoring, reporting (obligatory), communication to customers (non-committal), farm or product certification, landscape planning, farm advice or development, policy advice and research (Schader et al., 2014; Wustenberghs et al., 2015). At the farm level, ISATs have among others been used to benchmark farms worldwide and across farming sectors, to compare production systems (e.g. organic vs. conventional), to support multi-actor decision making and to design innovative production systems (Schader et al., 2016; Gésan-Guiziu, 2020). Most comprehensive ISATs do evaluate soil quality as a theme within the environmental dimension, e.g. in MOTIFS (Meul et al., 2008), RISE (Häni et al., 2003, Grenz et al., 2009), PGTool (Gerrard et al., 2012), SAFA (FAO, 2013) or SMART (Schader et al., 2016). However, to our knowledge, so far no ISATs have been developed specifically to evaluate SSM or changes in soil management.

Several ISATs, however, do aim at evaluating changes in farming practices. MASC, for example, is a qualitative multi-attribute decision model for *ex ante* assessment of the sustainability of changes in

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cropping systems. The model compares potential alternative cropping systems to the prevailing system. It encompasses three farm sustainability dimensions and can incorporate informal knowledge into the assessment, via the use of qualitative information (Sadok et al., 2009). MASC has been used to assess innovative cropping systems aiming to mitigate climate change (Craheix et al., 2014) and to evaluate the sustainability of conservation agriculture at the cropping system level (Craheix et al., 2016). Built on the same software basis as MASC, also DEXiPM (DEXi Pest Management) was developed for *ex ante* assessment of cropping systems' sustainability, particularly integrated crop management systems with a limited use of pesticides (Pelzer et al., 2012). Originally designed for arable crops, DEXiPM has also been adapted for use in field vegetables, grapevines and pomefruit orchards (Angevin et al., 2017; Caffi et al., 2017), while it can now also be implemented *ex post*.

locola *et al.* (2020) present a multi-criteria assessment able to assess rotations over several years. Their indicator set was designed to be sensitive to the holistic sustainability performance of crop diversification strategies. Thus to adequately represent trade-offs (e.g. enhanced ecosystem services countered with less profitability or increased costs of new practices) and carry-over effects within innovative rotations (e.g. reduced need for nitrogen fertilization after a leguminous crop, weed suppression in the succeeding crops after a ley). This ISAT was developed for and is being used in the DiverIMPACTS project (H2020 n°727482). It is implemented for critical *ex post* diagnosis of existing systems and for *ex ante* assessment of innovative cropping system scenarios. The assessment outcomes have allowed local actors to reflect on the effects generated by the new practices implemented.

An interesting innovation in the implementation of ISATs was introduced by Winter et al. (2020). Instead of assessing existing farms, as previously done, they used a typical farms approach. The typical farm is defined as the farm type that represents the mode of the distribution of farms, i.e. the farm that can be found most often on the ground. It thus differs from the average farm that depicts the mean of all farms and which rarely actually exists on the ground. Constructing typical farms is started from literature and then supplemented and verified by experts. In their sustainability assessment of coffee production systems Winter *et al.* (2020) applied the SMART-Farm Tool (Schader et al., 2016) to typical farms. SMART represents an operationalization of the SAFA framework (FAO, 2013), described in section 2.4. The data for the typical farm assessment was also collected through expert interviews. However, they encountered some difficulties when discussing the SMART indicators for the typical systems. Experts occasionally found it difficult to give an estimation in such detail as required by the SMART-Farm Tool. Winter *et al.* (2020) therefore suggest to use more general indicators for future expert judgements. Nevertheless, the typical farm approach seems interesting to assess sustainability in projects where the number of real farm cases is limited, such as in SoildiverAgro.

Two major critiques have been formulated regarding ISATs in recent years. The first concerns the lack of user-orientation in many existing ISATs, which is considered as one of the reasons for their low uptake in practice and the lack of integration of ISAT results into farmers' strategic decision making (Alrøe and Noe, 2016; de Olde et al., 2016, 2018; Coteur et al., 2018, 2020). Farmers perceive existing ISATs as not sufficiently mirroring their particular situation and values. ISATs thus need to be better tuned to farmers' needs, motivations and visions, especially if they are to be used in strategic decision

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making. A prerequisite is for all stakeholders, including farmers, to participate in the ISAT development (Schindler et al., 2015; Alroe and Noe, 2016; Coteur et al., 2018, 2020).

A second critique is that the assessment of the social dimension in multi-criteria assessments often is less developed than the economic and environmental dimensions (de Olde et al., 2018; Rööös et al., 2019; Janker and Mann, 2020). Some previous authors distinguished between internal social sustainability, reflecting the well-being of the farmer and his family and their perceptions of life quality, versus external social sustainability, related to society level demands and depending on its values and concerns (Dessein and Nevens, 2007; Meul et al., 2008; Lebacqz et al., 2013; Schader et al., 2014). Some ISATs mainly reflect the latter type of social sustainability, e.g. SAFA that strongly bases its assessments on human rights and clearly focuses on the situation of farmworkers (Rööös et al., 2019; Janker and Mann, 2020). Therefore, recent authors again call for a stronger inclusion of the farmers' view in ISATs, especially concerning the assessment of social sustainability (Rööös et al., 2019).

3.5 Policy level economic analysis

To build a model-based approach to evaluate alternative policy options and scenarios several previous empirical studies provide useful examples.

There are some examples of economic valuation of ecosystem services in the scientific literature. For a short overview see e.g. Tepes et al. (2020). However, there are few examples of systemic, model-based analyses of the valuation of different policy options that promote ecosystem services. Schwilch et al. (2018) provide an overview of the economic valuation of soil management measures and their effects on ecosystem services.

Brady et al. (2019) develop a roadmap to value soil ecosystem services in a multi-level decision-making approach. In their approach, they follow a multi-step process that has been extended from the farm level to the regional and national level, based on a regional case study for southern Sweden. To simulate the impact of alternative land management practices on agricultural production and ecosystem services at the regional level, an extended form of the agent-based AgriPoliS model was applied. What is new about this model-based approach by Brady et al. (2019) is the extension to include the aspect of food security and its linkage to the provision of ecosystem services. After introducing an approach to calculate the societal value of ecosystem services three alternative management scenarios of different proportions of grass cover in the crop rotation were tested. While this model-based approach makes a compelling contribution to quantifying and valuing ecosystem service production, it lacks a link to policies that address and promote soil health and soil biodiversity.

Lafuite, Denise and Loreau (2018) proposed a stylized approach in combining a general equilibrium market model with a dynamical system of demography, technological change and loss in biodiversity. With this combined modelling method they showed the importance of policies to preserve biodiversity as well as societal welfare. This model-based assessment clearly indicates the long-term positive effect of a so-called 'land depletion tax' on biodiversity and the resilience of society.

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To analyse the economy-wide impact of policy measures targeted to improve soil biodiversity and preserve the provision of ecosystem services regionalized data is a pre-condition. Here, Hein et al. (2020) propose an ecosystem accounting for the Netherlands to provide accounting tables of ecosystem type, condition, services, assets, carbon and biodiversity at high resolution level. Apart from this 'physical' accounting system Hein et al. extended this approach to quantify ecosystem services in monetary terms in alignment with information in the standard national accounting system.

These different approaches will help to setup a model-based approach to evaluate alternative policy options and scenarios in SoildiverAgro.

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4 Implementation of the approaches in SoildiverAgro and the integrated approach

The different theoretical, now empirically illustrated approaches which lay the foundation for the integrative assessment scheme, each have their own demands for data collection and analysis. The integrated assessment scheme aims to provide a coherent data collection framework for SoildiverAgro WP6. Each of the farm level approaches first define the starting points for the analysis, next management practices are familiarized, and data concerning practices collected with varying methods. When the farm related data, following the protocols developed around the theoretical strands, are collected, in the analysis stage again approach-specific tools will be used. Finally results are reported in a coherent way: all theoretical and methodological approaches for the different elements of the integrated assessment scheme similarly applied in the different study cases — with the exception of where data has not become available. In this section we first present the thematic approaches, and then provide interlinkages to guarantee the coherence and efficiency in the data collection and analyses for WP6.

4.1 Environmental assessment – developing soil biodiversity focused LCA on exemplary basis

The use of LCA allows the study of midpoint-level environmental impact categories, in addition to the main focus of the project, soil biodiversity, which is an endpoint-level impact category. When agricultural development takes a holistic viewpoint, and includes economic, environmental and socio-technical impacts along the whole life cycle LCA is of vital importance to avoid burden shifting among impact categories when applying the management practices tested in SoildiverAgro. It is not worth enhancing biodiversity if other environmental impact categories are going to be significantly affected.

An LCA will be performed within SoildiverAgro project following the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards. Consequently, the first step is defining the goal and scope of the assessment. The goal of the LCA is to assess the potential environmental impacts variations of the different management practices enhancing biodiversity compared to current practices.

The limits of the study will be coherent with the scope of the project and will be fixed at farm level, setting a cradle-to-gate LCA. This could present some limitations, given that downstream life cycle stages are excluded. However, in this project, the products obtained are assumed to present the same quality (in terms of expiration, nutritional content, etc.) than the products currently produced. On the other hand, the crop yield is an important factor in the environmental impacts and will be included.

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The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) will be fed with data from the case studies and updated and regionalized agricultural LCA databases (Agribalyse, World Food Database, Ecoinvent v3.6, etc). A detailed technical description of current and new management practices will be developed in the case studies (WP5), which will be used to develop the environmental and economic data inventories .

Inventory data will be modelled in specific software and the environmental impacts will be calculated using a Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method through classification and characterization of elementary flows. Special attention will be paid to categories such as land use or soil quality, climate change, acidification, eutrophication potential, and, as an end-point category, loss of biodiversity. If relevant, normalization and weighting factors will be applied to assess the decision-making phase. The LCIA methods to use will be selected according to the state-of-the-art. The methods recommended by the European Commission in the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) framework will be firstly used. Some variations could be done regarding pesticides and toxicity (OLCA-Pest) or compaction and water erosion impacts on agricultural soils, given that new approaches have been developed and could be tested in this project.

Finally, the results and conclusions will be shared with project partners to obtain feedback and obtain final conclusions considering the three pillars of sustainability and technical considerations.

4.2 Farm level economic analysis

The farm level economic analysis is based on partial crop budgeting techniques and focuses on gross margin (GM) that is defined as the difference between revenue (value of production plus subsidies) and all variable costs directly attributable to each crop. This simplifies the analysis by focusing on the crop production data that is strictly necessary for the analysis and that is compatible with data from experimental activities, and avoiding collecting economic data on the farm structure. Results can later be upgraded to approximate a value for farm profit using existing data for standard indirect costs from scientific literature or economic databases, such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN).

There are different secondary sources of technical and economic data on crop's GM, such as public national agricultural statistics, the FADN, rural development programmes or scientific literature. However, most of them provide technical information in a relatively aggregated manner or, in some cases, only provide economic values in monetary terms (e.g., the FADN), with little compatibility with the data provided by field experiments.

Experimental activities focus on the impact of changes in specific farming practices (fertilization, pest control, tillage, etc.). If the available GM data is not disaggregated to a very detailed level, it might be difficult to integrate the information from the experimental activities. For example, the fertilization cost savings from a given reduction in the amount of fertilizer applied might not be proportional to that reduction, as other inputs participate in such operation (labour, machinery, fuel). Enough technical detail on all fertilization operations would be required to assess such cost savings.

Additionally, if GM data is only available in monetary terms, even if it is very disaggregated, it would not be compatible with the experimental activities, as the unitary prices behind such monetary values

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would be unknown, and therefore the cost estimated from the experimental data (using different unitary prices) would not be comparable. Consequently, there is a need to build a detailed technical characterization of the standard crop production process in each study area that is compatible with the results of the experimental activities and allows their integration and comparability.

The basis for the farm level economic assessment of the tested soil biodiversity enhancement practices is thus the elaboration of a detailed technical-economic characterisation of the standard crop production process and farming practices in terms of yields, input use and production costs, including the consideration of the time dynamics of the production process. Such characterisation would serve as a benchmark for comparison with the results from the experimental plots where the different sustainable farming practices are tested.

We will now comment on the different steps to be taken.

The **first step is building a technical characterization of the standard crop production process** based on literature and/or consultation to farmers and/or experts. To that end, the productive process would be defined on the basis of the natural crop cycle, to be able to obtain the income and production costs associated with each production activity in a more direct and realistic manner (Ballesteros, 2000). Besides, the production cycle/process for each crop would be considered in isolation, even if the farms have more than one crop or productive process. Therefore, based on these methodological criteria, the production cycle must be understood as a double process, both agronomic and economic.

Consequently, the technical-economic characterization of the crops' production processes requires collecting detailed information on the different crop operations along the productive cycle. To that end, crop operations would be organised on a monthly basis, starting right after harvesting and ending in the harvesting of the following crop season, and per type of operations (ploughing, irrigation, fertilisation, weed and pest control, pruning, harvesting, etc.). Each farming operation can imply the use of labour and machinery, consumption of water and energy or the use of different materials. The data collected would be standardized to build a standard technical characterization of the production process for each crop, which would be defined by the different crop operations on a monthly basis.

Data to be collected on each crop's production process would therefore include: (1) quantity of production (crop yields); (2) use of inputs such as fertilisers, herbicides and other agrochemicals, energy and irrigation water (type of input, quantity applied, hours/number of applications, unitary price of inputs); (3) farm machinery used (type of machinery, crop operations, hours of use, fuel consumption, unitary prices, etc.); and (4) labour use (crop operations, working hours/days per operation, wages, etc.).

The source of data for the technical characterization of the production process can be bibliographical, interviews with farmers/experts and/or the description of the crop farming operations implemented in the experimental plots within WP5. Ideally, several sources of information should be used for cross validation. It might be the case that the characteristics of the crop production process in one study area present differences with those considered in the literature or in other secondary sources of data that would require consulting with local farmers or experts.

A recommended way of proceeding is building the technical characterization of the crop production process on the basis of the information on farming operations collected from the experimental plots, complemented with the consultation to relevant bibliography. Such characterization would then be validated with the help of some farmers and experts. Asking some farmers/experts to revise and provide feedback on the data collected, rather than asking them for such data, would minimize the time and effort taken for them, while allowing to focus on the major information gaps or in the aspects that are less clear.

This first step would be completed with the identification of those elements of the standard crop production process that are affected by the experimental treatments (e.g., yields, farming practices, input use, etc.). At the end, the technical characterization must clearly describe:

- The current farming system in each case study in terms of the type of farming operations performed, their timeline, input use, crop yields, etc. what must correspond to the reference or control treatments in the experimental design.
- The changes in terms of farming operations, use of inputs, crop yields, etc. that correspond to each of the treatments in the experimental design.

The **second step is the collection of technical data from experimental farms**. Technical data from the experimental plots would be collected using an Excel spreadsheet developed by UPCT in order to guarantee its compatibility with the characteristics of the standard production processes identified (see SoildiverAgro's deliverable 5.1). Only technical information would be collected from experimental plots, while economic information (such as wages, cost of inputs, O&M costs of machinery or irrigation equipment, etc.) would be obtained from both farmers and/or secondary sources of information.

This second step is not necessarily sequential with step 1, as it can run on parallel. Moreover, technical data collected from experimental plots can also be used to characterize the standard production process and to identify its elements affected by experimental activities.

A **third step consists of the collection of economic data** (crop selling price, input prices, labour cost, etc.) from secondary sources of information, farmers, technical advisors, input suppliers, etc.

The **fourth step is the economic characterization of the production process** to define the standard cost structure and crop budget. The standard economic characterization would be obtained from the technical one using input market prices and average market product prices, to allow for the standardization of production costs. Market crop prices would be calculated as the average detrended yearly price for each crop calculated using data from the official agricultural databases. The standardization of direct production costs allows to reduce biases and variabilities resulting from differences in the prices of inputs and eases the analysis of input use and the comparison of the impact of a shift in specific farming practices. The result is the standard direct costs structure and budget for each crop.

The **fifth step is the integration in the standard crop budget of the results from experimental activities**. The different experimental treatments imply changes in farming operations, input use and crop yields

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that results in changes in production costs and revenues. The integration of such changes in the standard crop budget results in a separate cost structure and budget for each experimental treatment, i.e., for each of the alternative farming practices tested.

The **sixth step is the calculation of financial and economic indicators for the different experimental treatments**. Once the crop cost structure and budget has been built for each experimental treatment, gross margin, as well as other profitability and productivity ratios can be calculated for comparing the different experimental treatments.

4.3 Measuring farmers interest to participate -TPB

TPB methodology will assess management practice specific behavioral intentions, attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. We also define the possible extensions to the standard TPB model as a **Step 1**.

We will select the practices from each region for evaluation, i.e. one practice that is region specific and possibly one practice that can be implemented across the regions (**Step 2**). The management practices need to be easily defined practices that can be described in a survey shortly and understandably.

The basis to implement TPB in SdA is to conduct semi-structured interviews (**Step 3**) to identify outcomes, referents and control factors for each of the single practices in the different regions. Interaction with stakeholders (WP2+5), may help here, or specific focus groups are organized. The questionnaire for a large scale survey to assess farmers beliefs on the control factors, outcomes and referents related to each of the practices will be constructed for each region.

The questionnaire for a large scale survey to assess farmers beliefs on the control factors, outcomes and referents related to each of the practices will be designed (**Step 4**). For all outcomes, referents and control factors, two question types will be asked. For each outcome, its likelihood will be assessed (e.g. "What is the likelihood that compost improves soil biodiversity?") with ordered scale, just as the degree to which a farmer believes this outcome is positive or negative. For each referent, the farmer will be asked to which degree the referent is positive or negative towards the practice: "My advisor is positive towards compost application" and to which degree he values the judgment of the referent. For each control factor, farmers will be asked to which degree this control factor makes applying the practice attractive/difficult. Additionally, we will ask the farmer to which degree a particular control factor applies on their farm (e.g. "Is the appropriate machinery available on your farm?"). Beyond the typical variables in TPB we also include variables, such as past behavior, identity, or environmental orientation, based on the semi-structured interviews.

The survey will be implemented in each region (**Step 5**). It assesses management practice specific behavioral intentions, attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. In the survey implementation following criteria are applied:

- Enough data for statistical modelling on each region for each practices (N >300)

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- Response rates are assumed to be around 15% in the calculation of total sample
- Sampling region: part of the pedoclimatic region where management practice is possible based on researcher evaluation
- Sample of farmers from the sampling region
- Online survey (LimeSurvey) with language versions: mobile important, e-mail invitation if possible.

In the analysis phase (**Step 6**) the survey data sets from each region are pooled and analysed individually. Structural equation modelling is applied. Finally the results will be reported (**Step 7**).

4.4 Building a custom integrated sustainability assessment and implementing it in SoildiverAgro

Given the recent critiques about the lack of farmer orientation in existing integrated sustainability assessment tools (ISATs), especially concerning social sustainability (Alrøe and Noe, 2016; de Olde et al., 2016, 2018; Coteur et al., 2018, 2020; Røos et al., 2019), it is recommended for all stakeholders, including farmers, to participate in the ISAT development, in order to tune them better to farmers' needs, motivations and visions and overcome the subjectivity of researcher-led design (Schindler et al., 2015; Alrøe and Noe, 2016; Coteur et al., 2018, 2020, Mullender, 2020). Section 4.2 already describes a procedure to co-design the standard production process needed for economic assessment. In this section, we refine this procedure towards integrated sustainability assessment.

The FAO (2013) distinguishes four steps in the procedure of a SAFA sustainability assessment: (1) Mapping, i.e. setting goals and scope for the assessment; (2) Contextualisation; (3) Selecting tools and indicators; (4) Assessment and reporting. We propose to go through all the phases in a participatory, co-designing setting, integrating top-down (researchers) and bottom-up (stakeholders' perspective) approaches. In the context of SoildiverAgro, the Communities of Practitioners created in Task 8.3 may offer opportunities for engaging stakeholders in this research.

Step 1: Setting goals, scope and boundaries of the assessment

The **goal** of the integrated sustainability assessment follows from the project's goal: "the selection and adoption of new management practices and cropping systems that enhance soil genetic and functional biodiversity to reduce the use of external inputs while increasing crop production and quality, the delivery of ecosystem services and the EU agricultural stability and resilience". The integrated assessment should obviously support this goal and support farmers' decision making process by providing them with a holistic view of their farm's sustainability when implementing new management practices. To do so, the ISAT should integrate previous WP5 and WP6 assessments and fill the gaps not yet assessed in previous assessments.

The **scope** of the assessment includes four elements (FAO, 2013; Schader et al., 2014):

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- The **thematic scope** relates to the sustainability dimensions assessed. In the integrated assessment at least the environmental, economic and social dimensions are assessed simultaneously. Whether in the case of SoildiverAgro also the governance dimension is relevant, will need to be co-decided in the “contextualisation” step.
- The **geographical scope** describes the area in which the assessment can be applied. In our case, it should at least cover all the areas where innovative farming practices are being tested, i.e. the whole of Europe.
- The **sector scope** of the assessment can be either specific, i.e. applicable to specific products or farm types, or general, i.e., applicable to all agricultural products or farm types. In the case of SoildiverAgro a wide variety of crop production needs to be included, but the stakeholder group may decide to exclude animal husbandry.
- The **temporal scope** remains to be discussed. The assessment may be confined to one isolated production cycle, but in view of the build-up of soil biodiversity, it may be more logical to assess a complete rotation, so that trade-offs and carry over effects can be evaluated. Iocola et al. (2020) presented a procedure for such an assessment.

Finally, the **boundaries** of the assessment need to be discussed. For farm level sustainability assessments a common boundary adopted is the farm gate (e.g. Meul et al., 2008; de Olde et al., 2016). However, in SoildiverAgro the boundary may also be set at the sale of crop products, again excluding animal husbandry.

Step 2: Contextualisation

According to the FAO (2013), the contextualisation step comprises listing relevant themes and subthemes and compiling relevant contextual data. In SoildiverAgro, however, this work will need to be preceded by the determination of a reference system, i.e. what are the standard production systems against which the innovative production systems will be benchmarked?

As for the economic assessment (section 4.2), we propose to **co-design the reference system** using a two phase procedure. First the “typical farm”, applying the standard production process, is described as far as possible from the existing literature and data such as the FADN. This construct should represent the mode of all farms in a particular region, i.e. the farm that can be found most often on the ground (Winter et al., 2020). The characteristics of this farm should then be elaborated further and validated in a workshop with experts and farmers. Experts may be the authors of relevant literature, extension services, etc. Snowball sampling is a crucial part of the expert selection as it gets first-hand information on who belongs to the circle of experts in the respective area and minimizes the chances of leaving relevant interview partners out (Winter et al., 2020). The inclusion of farmers in the stakeholder group is evident as we want to tackle the critiques concerning the lack of user-orientation and increase the ownership of the end-users of the entire assessment procedure.

Characteristics that need to be addressed in this process include among others the typical farm size, the combination of crops grown and the rotation implemented, the typical crop yields, the amount of labour available on the farm (farmer, family and external labour), the inputs used in the production system, typical labouring practices, machinery used, etc. The characteristics listed should later allow

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to assess indicators such as the emissions typically associated with inputs or machinery use, etc. These characteristics can, of course, vary greatly from one agricultural subsector to another and from one European region to another. A reference system thus needs to be constructed for per subsector and per region, in which innovative practices are experimented in SoildiverAgro.

Compiling relevant contextual data in the case of SoildiverAgro in first instance means taking all the data collected in WP5 and the previous WP6 tasks into account and integrating them into this assessment to the largest possible extent. If needed these data can be complemented with literature and expert knowledge.

Step 3: Theme, subtheme and indicator selection

Iocola et al. (2020) describe a **co-design process for an actor-oriented multi-criteria assessment** that can be conveyed to the SoildiverAgro project. The researchers based their methodology on the SAFA (FAO, 2013). From the 21 themes and 58 subthemes in SAFA (Figure 2), they first selected the ones they felt were important to articulate the benefits and disadvantages of the practices experimented in their project. They also compiled an initial list of indicators they considered relevant to assess the selected (sub)themes. These initial lists were then confronted with stakeholder perspectives in a series of co-design workshops, in which feedback and suggestions for further areas of interest to be studied were collected. Based on the stakeholders' input, the researchers compiled a final list of (sub)themes and a list of potential indicators. In a second round of stakeholder workshops, indicator relevance, ease of understanding and computational problems were discussed, after which the indicator set was finalised.

An alternative method for participatory (sub)theme and indicator selection is the Delphi-style approach described by Mullender et al. (2020). Also this method is based on SAFA and starts with an initial list of (sub)themes and indicators compiled by researchers. Indicator selection, however, proceeds through three rounds of stakeholder surveys, with one intermediate workshop. The authors found this method particularly valuable for international projects, with stakeholders across multiple countries that potentially have very different perspectives on sustainability. They did, however, include one face-to-face discussion round into the Delphi procedure, as they felt this provides a valuable means for information exchange and a move towards consensus amongst stakeholders.

In SoildiverAgro, the pre-selection of themes, subthemes and indicators by the researchers will comprise a comparison of the indicators resulting from WP5 and previous WP6 sections. They will be set off against the SAFA framework (Figure 2). For example the soil quality and soil biodiversity result from WP5, while the aboveground biodiversity is not yet covered. The greenhouse gas emissions, material and energy use should be covered by the LCA, while parts of the air and water quality may not be covered, should it be decided not to include pesticides and toxicity in the LCA. Similarly, the economic analysis described above covers profitability, but not the vulnerability themes in the SAFA's economic resilience theme.

A co-design process, using either of the methods above, will decide on which (sub)themes should be addressed additionally to fill the gaps and on the indicators to use. Given (1) the critique that the social

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dimension in multi-criteria assessments often is underdeveloped (de Olde et al., 2018; Rööös et al., 2019; Janker and Mann, 2020); (2) the fact that previous WP6 assessments only concern the environmental and economic dimensions and (3) the SAFA strongly basing its social dimension on human rights and the wider social impact of farming (external social sustainability); the indicator selection process in SoildiverAgro will need to devote substantial attention to the inclusion of indicators reflecting the well-being of the farmer and his family and their perceptions of life quality (internal social sustainability).

Step 4: Assessment and reporting

Finally, the customised indicator set will need to be assessed for the reference system and for the experimented innovative systems. For the environmental and economic dimensions, much of the necessary data will flow through from WP5 and previous WP6 assessments. Whenever this is not possible, and for the social dimension, **data collection** will be done **through stakeholder consultation**, i.e. experts and farmers will be asked to rate the remaining indicators. Winter et al. (2020), used individual interviews to do so. In SoildiverAgro we might also use the opportunities provided by the workshops or surveys organised for the previous indicator selection step or the surveys used to assess farmers' willingness to adopt the experimented innovative practices (section 4.3).

Concerning the need for expert rating, Winter et al. (2020) do propose a restriction on the indicator selection in step 3. For their assessment they used the SMART Farm Tool (Schader et al., 2016). They encountered some difficulties when discussing "typical" systems. Experts occasionally found it difficult to provide estimates for these constructs, especially in such detail as required by the SMART-Farm Tool. They therefore recommend the use of more general indicators for future expert judgements.

Finally, the results of the ISAT design process and of the assessment will be presented in a separate **report**, apart from the planned deliverables for WP6.

4.5 Model-Based Assessment of Policy Options

In SoilDiverAgro we aim to test management practices and cropping systems beyond farm and regional level and to assess their implementation potential, the related costs and benefits at national and EU level.

This economic analysis will be performed in line with the integrated framework presented here making use of the outcomes of farm-level analysis which are complemented by results generated in the field experiments, through surveys as well as secondary data sources.

The CBA will allow us to compare all costs and benefits directly and indirectly linked to different farming practices. To find out shadow prices for externalities identified by the LCA we will apply the benefit transfer methodology. In order to apply the benefit transfer methodology, the first step is to conduct a survey on the academic literature that has previously estimated shadow prices for the relevant midpoints of interest in SoilDiverAgro LCA.

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To that end, the CE Delft environmental prices handbook by de Bruyn (2018) provides estimations of shadow prices for relevant midpoint categories. It represents the most comprehensive and in depth guide for shadow prices in the context of the EU28. Reports from the CE Delft environmental prices handbook are closely linked to the Recipe method for LCA. The most updated Recipe methodology and CE Delft environmental prices handbook will be used. A major issue in SoilDiverAgro is to ensure compatibility between methodologies applied to LCA and CBA.

The 'upscaling' at national and EU level will be applied by a market model (computable general equilibrium model) approach which covers not only the economics of agri-food markets but also the related instruments of agriculture, environmental and sustainability policies, such as SDG-related policies and last but not least, the policy instruments of the new-CAP following the ideas of the Farm-To-Fork- and the Green Deal-Strategies of the EU Commission. While changes in the cropping practices of individual farmers would not require a market model. If (almost) all farmers, however, adjust their cropping practices, e.g. in a significant reduction of fertilizer and pesticide applications, in changes in crop rotations, or in changes in land uses due to further environmental restrictions, supply responses become obvious. If the EU, as one of the largest supplier in agricultural products, will change or limit its supply potential by more restrictive policies, repercussions to the global agri-food markets are reasonable to be expected.

For this part of the analysis the calculations will be done with the market model MAGNET (Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool), that is a sequential dynamic General Equilibrium (CGE) Model covering the world economy including all relevant agents with focus on inter-sectoral and inter-regional relations (Woltjer and Kuiper, 2014). While all products are enclosed in the model, particular attention is given to agri-food and its trade. The model depicts historic time series for product and factor prices, alongside with data on production, consumption and trade until the most recent year available in global data bases, e.g. FAOSTAT Data allowing medium-term projections. While MAGNET is traditionally deployed for trade policy analysis (Kavallari et al., 2014), here we use it to assess the effects of a more environmental-friendly crop production practices and its implications on yields and supply over time, exemplified for the major crops in the EU. This approach includes the outcome of the CBA- and LCA-analysis to illustrate that changing cropping practices not only affects yields, but also has long-term effects on the economic viability of the farming sector as well as on trade in agricultural commodities. This is particularly true for wheat and other cereals. Because of its global importance for human consumption and as feed, wheat, corn and barley are products for which detailed data series have been introduced into MAGNET. Long-term historical data on yields are recalibrated on the basis of FAOSTAT data. Commodity flows are available for all major wheat producing regions across the globe, disaggregated at country level for the bigger wheat producers.

The target year of this modeling approach will be 2030 to perform simulations in order to take into account the time lapse between the change of practices and environmental benefits. Those benefits that cannot be measured monetarily will be integrated in the economic assessment using multi-criteria analysis techniques. These simulations will help to assess the potential of the tested management practices at national level as well as across the EU, their economic performance and the delivery of the ecosystem services related to the adapted management practices.

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The effects of several scenarios will be simulated, such as market penetration with the crops produced with soil biodiversity promoting management or prices for high quality products. A similar approach will be used to assess operational biodiversity (or other SDG-related) targets. Here different levels of soil biodiversity achieved through implementation of empirically tested management practices compared with current crop management will be analyzed in the economic modelling framework. Again, this approach will allow us to analyse the consequences of different crop management practises not only at the farm but also at the market level.

4.6 Integrated approach

Figure 3 shows the intergrated approach for implementation of SdA WP6. We may identify several shared phases in the approaches (tasks in WP6) that take place on the farm level. Some of the phases are, however, approach specific. Tasks will benefit from identifying possibilities for standardization of the processes and testing of management practices analysis across approaches using the characterizations from WP5. Stakeholder workshops can provide verification for the descriptions of production processes (6.2.1 and 6.2.2), identify relevant effects of practices (6.2.1 and 6.2.3) and indicator selection (6.2.4). Tasks that use secondary data can also identify opportunities to cooperate. The survey conducted in 6.2.3 can offer possibilities to supplement data for other tasks in WP6. Even though the analyses phase in each farm level task is independent. Policy level economic analysis relies especially on farm level economic analysis but can benefit also from other farm level tasks. Finally, all the approaches provide information for the cross case study comparative analysis (task 6.3.3)

Figure 3. Integrated assessment for the environmental-socio-economic assessment in SoildiverAgro WP6.

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5 Concluding remarks

The interdisciplinary socio-economic and environmental analysis in SoildiverAgro has various aims. It provides information for decision makers of the effects of management practices to support either farm or policy level decision making but it also offers tools to understand farmers' choice and factors affecting them. Some of the approaches used in WP6 utilize objective information and some of them rely on decision makers' perceptions. Time frame and ways to integrate time in the analysis vary. Some of the approaches operate on a physical level, and some use monetary measures. Due to these differences it is obvious that full integration of the approaches on the theoretical level is not possible and would not lead to a meaningful entity. Our integrated approach to soil sustainability assessment results from a range of theoretical strands, which are combined into an assessment tool which aims to support cooperation towards efficient and feasible integrative assessment in WP6.

Basis for successful cooperation is mutual understanding of the concepts used in each of the approaches. Summaries of approaches explained aims, basic concepts, and their assumed links. The reviews of previous empirical studies showed the knowledge gaps. In each of the approaches there exist a number of empirical studies concerning agricultural practices but applications targeting soil conservation are rather rare.

Finally, the descriptions of the research process in each approach provided possibilities to identify especially the links between the approaches. These links were identified in characterization of management practices and identifying their physical effects. The possibilities for efficient research processes were recognized, the practical work in WP6 will reveal how cooperation will be realized in practice.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

